

THE RIGHT CHOICE OF LITERATURE

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Annotation: *This article provides a comparative analysis of the teaching of English and world literature. The content of literature textbooks for schoolchildren was analyzed. The pages devoted to world literature in the textbooks, the impact of the examples given in them on the minds of students were discussed.*

Keywords: *literature context, textbook content, new program, State Education Standard*

In recent years, there have been various discussions of critics in world literature. Given that the ideas put forward in examples of western or eastern literature that do not fit the mentality of a particular country affect the minds of students, compiling textbook content is a very important task. In addition, it is natural that there are difficulties in the process of using a methodology that harmonizes local and global samples of world literature and providing an acceptable approach for students. If the topic is chosen in a way that is appropriate for the student's age and national mentality, it will give the student an intercultural closeness, an expansion of the student's imagination, and the opportunity to live in some part of the imaginary world. Tsvetan Todorov "Why literature?" He wrote about his acquaintance with the world of books before he reached school age:

related to the time I was surrounded by books. There would be a lot of books in our house. I re-read the classic masterpieces of children's literature, such as "Arab Evenings," "Brothers Grimm and Anderson's Tales," "Tom Sawyer," and "Oliver Twist." Todorov proved that reading a particular regional text provides an opportunity to get acquainted with the proximity to the region, the general environment and the local context. "Literary science is crucial in shaping the personality traits of the reader. The main goal is for the writer to enter the world of creativity and thereby develop the child's mind and taste. The masterpieces of Uzbek and world literature, which are included in textbooks and collections, are important in enriching the minds and emotions of students. "2 The main issue is not only in the teaching of national literature. "Literature" is related to the content of sections devoted to world literature in textbooks. The literature textbook of the 6th grade Uzbek student consists of two parts, in which only the life and work of Gianni Rodari are addressed from the series of world literature. The

adventure works of plab writers can serve to expand the imagination of the reader, to form their interests. representatives Jack London and the life and work of Alfonse Dode. The stories "Love for Life" and "The Last Lesson" are exemplary and very useful for the same teenage children. In these stories, qualities such as patriotism, humanity, diligence, courage are glorified. But it's hard to say that Rashod Nuri Guntegin's "Cholikushi," which is included in the content of a literature book designed for 11th graders, was chosen correctly. "According to the novel, Farida sits in the middle of a huge tree and watches the relationship between Cameron and Nariman. I don't think it's ethical for 11th graders to read a 15-year-old girl's romantic adventures in their book. there are many works that affect his psyche, change his outlook on life, encourage him to make serious decisions.

It is true that the preparation of textbooks is a difficult task, but it is also a responsible one that affects the upbringing of the younger generation. Neither advanced technology nor pedagogical skills can distort the content of a textbook if it is damaged or disproportionate. To do this, it is possible to attract new lessons to work on the content without changing and republishing the cover every 4 years. I think it is important for all of us to prepare textbooks that are suitable for children's age and the Uzbek mentality.

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